

Technical
University
of Munich

WORLD CONFERENCE ON
TIMBER ENGINEERING 2025
BRISBANE, AUSTRALIA

Advancing Timber for the Future Built Environment

Trends in the development of innovative timber products in the construction market in Europe

Vanesa Baño¹, Peter Romih¹,
Jan-Willem van de Kuilen², Uwe Kies¹

¹ InnovaWood, Belgium | ² Technical University of Munich, Germany
<https://doi.org/10.52202/080513-0514> | uwe.kies@innovawood.eu
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15804518>

Funded by
the European Union

WCTE Conference
Brisbane, Australia, June 25, 2025

InnovaWood

The European Network
for **Wood** Research,
Innovation and Education

connect - share - influence

82 member organisations

30 countries

EU-funded projects

European Forest Research and Innovation Ecosystem

- Delivers a Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda for forestry and the forest-based sector
- Implementation measures and stakeholder commitments co-designed in a multi-actor approach
- Preparation of the European Partnership for Forests for co-programming of future funding

Grant no. 101081788, RIA, 2022-2026

Coordinator EFI, Finland

16 partners, 3.9 mio €

cordis/101081788 | eufore.eu

Empowering climate-smart, circular, and zero-waste use of underutilized wood from the forest and building stock in the construction sector to support the New European Bauhaus

- Underutilised wood species and material streams
- Zero-waste and circular building designs
- Assessing human health and well-being aspects by co-creation activities

Grant no. 101181021, RIA, 2024-2028

Coordinator University of Gent, Belgium

13 partners, 6.8 mio €

cordis/101181021 | woodstockproject.eu

Technical
University
of Munich

WORLD CONFERENCE ON
TIMBER ENGINEERING 2025
BRISBANE, AUSTRALIA

Advancing Timber for the Future Built Environment

Overview

- **Intro:** Wood products regulated by CEN
- **Results:** Trends of innovative products
- **Conclusions:** Main observations, further research needs
- **Outlook:** Wood innovation challenges

Timber construction in Europe

State of play

- Construction is dominated by energy-intensive materials (concrete 90% of weight) → **39%** of global GHG emissions
- Wood in construction globally: only 1.4% of weight, or **7%** of volume. Europe: only **3%** of volume
- EWP** like CLT, GLT, LVL are slowly gaining scale in the market (leading: Austria, Germany, Sweden).
- Wood construction can become a lever for decarbonization of the construction sector. → Need for more innovation

Main challenge

- How to leverage more EWP and scale up the market?

Figure 1. Sankey diagram of wood flow in EU-27 by industry and market in 2021. Adapted from Orfanidou et al. 2024.

Wood products regulated by CEN

Certification of products

- The Construction Products Regulation (CPR) lays down harmonised rules for the marketing of construction products in the EU. All products to be commercialized must obtain the **CE marking**.
- **Mature products** are regulated by harmonised EN standards (hEN).
- Technical Committees define the hEN :
TC 124 Timber structures, 10 product types
TC 112 Wood-based panels, 10 types
TC 88 Thermal insulating materials, 3 types
- **Innovative products** require an alternative route: manufacturers must apply for a European Technical Assessment (ETA) specific for each individual product.

Results: Trends of innovative products

Products with ETA certificates

PA ¹	Product type	by type	by PA
PA 13	Connectors	333	468
	Structural products for slabs	66	
	Other structural products	61	
	Systems	8	
PA 4	Thermal insulation products, composite insulation kits/systems	93	93
PA 34	Building kits, units, prefabricated elements	68	68
PA 14	Wood-based panels	25	25
PA 19	Flooring	12	12
PA 33	Fixings	8	8
PA 21	Wall/ceiling finishings and partitions	8	8
PA 9	Curtain Walls	1	1
PA 12	Road equipment	1	1
ETAG	Several (ETAG used as EAD)	160	160
TOTAL		844	

Table 4. Quantification of innovative products by product type (see full table in the article)

Top product sub-types

- Timber building kits: **162** (53 + 109 in ETAG)
- Three-dimensional nailing plates: **161** (158 + 3 in ETAG)
- Screws and threaded rods: **142**
- CLT- Solid wood slab elements: **55**

Interesting novelties

- Wood dowel** type fasteners: 3
- GLT made of **hardwood**: 3
- Modular** construction systems: 8
- Boards made from **recycled** beverage cartons: 2

Results: Trends of innovative products

Products with ETA certificates

PA ¹	Product type	by type	by PA
PA 13	Connectors	333	468
	Structural products for slabs	66	
	Other structural products	61	
	Systems	8	
PA 4	Thermal insulation products, composite insulation kits/systems	93	93
PA 34	Building kits, units, prefabricated elements	68	68
PA 14	Wood-based panels	25	25
PA 19	Flooring	12	12
PA 33	Fixings	8	8
PA 21	Wall/ceiling finishings and partitions	8	8
PA 9	Curtain Walls	1	1
PA 12	Road equipment	1	1
ETAG	Several (ETAG used as EAD)	160	160
TOTAL		844	

Table 4. Quantification of innovative products by product type (see full table in the article)

Figure 7: Examples of innovative products in wood construction

Results: Trends of innovative products

PA 13. Timber structures: Connectors

Nailing plates	Screws and threaded rods	Dowel-type fasteners with resin coating	Screws for use in nailing plates	Glued-in rods for timber connections	Plywood dovetail for CLT	Other
ETA 22/0002	ETA 11/0425	ETA 21/0778	ETA 04/0013	ETA_19/0752	ETA18/0254	ETA 23/0330

PA 13. Timber structures: Structural wood products

CLT- Solid wood slab elements	Dowel jointed solid wood slab elements	Prefabricated wood slab/wall element	Composite wood-based beams	Load-bearing skin panels	Beam or wall made of timber logs	Hardwood GLT
ETA 06/0138	ETA 18/0960	ETA 15/0760	ETA 23/0669	ETA 18/1014	ETA 11/0219	ETA 18/1018

Figure 7: Examples of innovative products in wood construction

Results: Trends of innovative products

PA 4. Thermal insulation products				PA 33. Fixings		
Insulation products made of vegetable fibres	ETICS for the use on timber frame buildings	Acoustic insulation made of biobased fibers	ETICS for wall made of timber	Minerally-bonded boards made of wood chips	Anchor devices	Fasteners for fixing of ETICS on timber constructions
ETA 17/0622	ETA 16/0997	ETA 07/0214	ETA 23/0811	ETA 19/0427	ETA 21/0260	ETA 20/0670
PA 14. Wood based panels		PA 34. Building kits		PA 9. Curtain walls		PA 19. Flooring
Prefabricated load-bearing skin panels and SIP panels	Timber building kits	Load bearing steel-wood roofs	Wood composite panels for façades	Terrace decking kit	Underlay of granulated PU foam and cork	
ETA 23/0526	ETA 22/0041	ETA 23/0669	ETA 15/0473	ETA 23/0631	ETA 23/0919	ETA 23/0077

Figure 7: Examples of innovative products in wood construction

Results: Trends of innovative products

Figure 4. Classification of innovative products in wood construction

Figure 5: Number of issued ETA versions

Highlights

- Highest activity in PA 13 “Structural timber products elements and ancillaries”: **468**
- Various products have pending categorization (ETAG): **160**
- Increasing in last decade: **100+** ETAs issued per year.
- Products are continuously enhanced (new ETA versions).
- German, Austrian and Italian companies are top 3 countries: 360 ETAs = **42%**
- Companies in non-EU countries also use ETAs (UK, Taiwan, etc).

Figure 6: Number of issued ETAs per country.

Conclusions

Main observations

- European Technical Assessments (ETAs)
Alternative route for CE approval, when harmonised standards are not (yet) available.
ETAs represent a **rich data source** for the study of innovative products.
- Commercial innovative products/systems
Their **number is constantly increasing** (+80 per year).
Most dynamic are connectors, slabs, building kits and insulation products.
- EN regulations and standards
Novel types of innovations are challenging for categorisation.
Complex, long procedures for updating and harmonisation, so the slow pace of regulations is limiting the upscaling of innovations (to some extent).

Conclusions

Further research

- **Deeper analysis of ETAs**
What are the application areas, product functionalities, performance levels?
Which types of companies and business models are driving these innovations?
- Market success of innovative products
What is their real impact? How disruptive are they?
- Mature products in hEN standards
Similar analysis as for ETAs, in collaboration with CEN Technical Committees
- **EN standards for strength grading of wood species in Europe**
Prepare for use of alternative species in the future

➤ In general, **more systematic research on the role of innovations and market uptake in the wood sector is needed**, to inform businesses, policy and regulatory bodies.

Outlook: Wood innovation - levels and scales

Skills & Education - Digitalisation - Competitiveness - Circular Economy

Let's innovate with wood!

Flèche de Cupidon, réalisation étudiants Ecole Supérieure du Bois esb@2025

© ESB 2025

connect - share - influence

innovawood.eu